

Speculation on Scaling, Maximum Entropy and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics Part 5

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Newtonian mechanics and special relativity are deterministic theories. This means that they do not use probability. We suggest, however, that it implies more than this. These theories use deterministic variables such as rest mass, m_0 , and x and t with infinite resolution. We suggest that focusing on the variables used in a deterministic theory is just as important as noticing that there is no probability.

Nature seems to contain explicit probabilistic examples, such as n -slit interference-diffraction and reflection-refraction. These are not described by deterministic Newtonian mechanics or deterministic special relativity. (In particular, the reflection and refraction probabilities for one dimensional reflection-refraction are not calculated using Newtonian mechanics even though one may obtain Snell's Law from conservation of momentum parallel to the n_1 - n_2 index of refraction interfaces.)

The question we consider in this note is: How does one deal with variables such as m_0 , x and t in a probabilistic theory? m_0 , rest mass, seems to be a deterministic variable as do x and t if measured by an external ruler and clock. In other words, at first glance a probabilistic theory seems to consist of deterministic variables which seems like a contradiction. We suggest that even though rest mass, m_0 , is deterministic, one may base x and t gradations of E and p such that the products Edt and pdx for these gradations are independent of any determinism. Furthermore, in Part I, we argued that the deterministic m_0 may be viewed as proportional to a probability. This can be carried further to create a Lorentz invariant $-Edt+pdx$ which is also independent of determinism due to dx and dt being expressed in terms of $1/p$ and $1/E$. This, in turn, leads to a quantum free particle viewpoint. Thus, we suggest that it is the desire to remove determinism from products of variables in special relativity which gives rise to the quantum probabilistic viewpoint. This extends the ideas of Part I.

Newtonian and Special Relativistic Determinism

Newtonian mechanics and special relativity are deterministic. This seems to be a statement of the lack of probabilities appearing in the theory, but we suggest that it is as much a statement about the variables used. Rest mass is deterministic and can be measured. x and t are also deterministic, have infinite resolution, and may be measured by an external ruler and clock.

Explicit Probability in Nature

We suggest that examples of explicit probabilistic scenarios exist in nature. These include n -slit interference-diffraction and reflection-refraction. These cannot be described in terms of Newtonian mechanics or special relativity. Snell's Law may be obtained using conservation of momentum parallel to the n_1 - n_2 index of refraction interface, but the one dimensional probability to reflect and refract cannot be obtained from Newtonian physics.

Probability and Deterministic Variables

The main point of this note is to suggest that even though there are deterministic variables in Newtonian mechanics and special relativity, a re-thinking of these variables may be needed in a probabilistic theory. Rest mass, m_0 , seems to be deterministic. The notion of an x position relative to an origin or a time relative to $t=0$ also seems to be deterministic. The question then becomes: Is there any way to somehow remove the sense of determinism from variables? It seems that the variables themselves cannot have their determinism changed. In Part I, however, we suggested that the deterministic rest mass, m_0 , may also be argued to be proportional to a probability for an internal decay. Thus, it may be viewed as both a deterministic and probabilistic variable. One may then establish time intervals representing average internal events. These would be proportional to:

$$1/m_0 \quad ((1))$$

Thus, dt is now also probabilistic and one has the invariant:

$$M_0 (1/m_0) = \text{rest mass} * dt \quad ((2))$$

If one performs a Lorentz transformation on $(0, m_0)$, one obtains an E and p :

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((3b))$$

If m_0 is considered to be a probability and it maps into E and p , these too should represent probabilities, it seems. The question is then: What probabilities do they represent? $|p|$ is the magnitude of momentum, but momentum is a vector which may point in any direction in 3-space. E , on the other hand, is a number. If one considers the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et + p \cdot r \quad ((4))$$

Then for $r=0$, one simply has E representing the entire system. This suggests that E should act like $m_0 c^2$ and represent a probability in time linked to a period:

$$\hbar/E \quad ((5))$$

Then: $E \hbar/E = \hbar$ which shows no deterministic variable. Similarly, if $t=0$, then p magnitude may represent a spatial gradation along the direction of p , i.e.

$$\hbar/|p| \quad ((6))$$

The Lorentz invariant then becomes independent of the deterministic variables, i.e

$$-E dt + p dx = -E n \hbar/E + p n \hbar/|p| = 0 \quad ((7))$$

In other words, in a probabilistic scheme, m_0 , E and $|p|$ actually represent probabilities and one has to create dx and dt so that they too are linked to probabilities. The Lorentz invariant $-Edt+pdx$ then removes all information about deterministic variables. On the other hand, $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$ ($c=1$) is an equation linking squares of probabilities.

Given that gradations ((5)) and ((6)), one may create a probability $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$ which contains the uniform probability distribution $p(x)$ as argued in Part 4. This then leads to free particle quantum mechanics.

In other words, we suggest that a probabilistic theory goes beyond simply providing probability functions, it actually changes some deterministic variables such as m_0 , E , $|p|$ and dx , dt to have them describe probabilistic notions.

Dual Determinism and Probability

We have focused above on the probabilistic and deterministic viewpoints as being separate, but they seem to be related. $v = x'/t'$ for constant v . Even if one has gradations \hbar/E and $\hbar/|p|$, x' and t' represent deterministic positions in $x-t$ regardless of the gradations used. Furthermore, the Lorentz transformation matrix is obtained by using deterministic considerations and these lead to the invariant $A = -Et + px$.

We have noted before that $-Et + px$, based on determinism, gives rise to $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/|p|$ due to degeneracies in A . The point we make in this note is that even the special relativistic invariant A may be interpreted in both a probabilistic and deterministic manner. As noted, one may obtain the Lorentz matrix by arguing that a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t should transform to x', t' such that $v = x'/t'$ when viewed from a frame moving at constant $-v$.

We have also argued that if m_0 is probability, then the product, $m_0 dt$ with $dt = 1/m_0$ removes any notion of this variable. If m_0 is seen as E and p in a moving frame and these are considered to be probabilities, then one may create an invariant which removes E and p . This invariant, however, could be any function of $f(E \cdot \hbar/E, p \cdot \hbar/p)$.

In the above discussion, we link it to the linear case Et and px found in the Lorentz invariant A because the deterministic rest mass m_0 is simultaneously a probability. Thus, there seems to be a dualism of probability and probability. This dualism, however, requires that one consider a dt and dx which remove all information of E and p in the Lorentz invariant $-Edt + pdx$. In other words, this is more than an invariant linked to moving frames.

As a final note, one may see that if in a rest frame, m_0 is proportional to a probability, then one has $dt = 1/m_0$ gradations. Simply using Lorentz transformations yields:

$$(0, 1/m_0) \text{ and } (0, 2/m_0) \rightarrow (x' = gv/m_0, g/m_0) \text{ and } (x' = 2gv/m_0, 2g/m_0) \quad ((8))$$

In other words, a dt interval $1/m_0$ in the rest frame is linked with dx' and dt' intervals as seen in the moving frame, but these do not give \hbar/E and $\hbar/|p|$ because they are based on deterministic arguments. We use $dx = \hbar/|p|$ and $dt = \hbar/E$ to remove any notion of E and p

from the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ rather than transform dt in the rest frame into dx' , dt' . Thus, something more than special relativistic frame transformations is being considered when developing free particle quantum mechanics from special relativity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a probabilistic theory seems to involve more than simply probability functions. It may also affect the variables used. For example, we argue that the deterministic variables m_0 , E and $|p|$ are actually proportional to probabilities for internal events and argue that one may construct dt and dx intervals, \hbar/E and $\hbar/|p|$, which remove the external ruler and clock from the picture and make the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ a more general one than simply one which focuses on different moving frames. In other words, we suggest deterministic-probabilistic dualism, with the emergence of $\exp(ipx)$ requiring more ideas than those provided by special relativity, but due to the dualism, one may still use special relativity to find the form of the probabilistic dx and dt values from $-Et+px$.